

MODELING THE RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE SHELLS CONTAINING MULTIPLE DELAMINATIONS

Fu-Kuo Chang and Zafer Kutlu
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Stanford University, Stanford, California 94305

ABSTRACT

An analytical model was developed for analyzing the response of laminated composite panels containing multiple delaminations. It was of particular interest to determine the buckling and post-buckling behavior of laminated composite plates and cylindrical shells containing cross-the-width delaminations. The model consists of a structural analysis for calculating the global deformations of the structures and a fracture analysis for determining delamination growth in the structures. A Lagrange multiplier technique was developed for the model to account for the delamination surface interaction. A nonlinear finite element code based on the updated Lagrangian formulation was developed for the model. The code can be used to simulate the response of flat and cylindrical composite panels containing one or two through-the-width delaminations from the initial loading to the final collapse.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination in laminated composites can significantly reduce the load-carrying capability of the structures. Therefore, the objective of this investigation was to study the buckling and post-buckling behavior of the composite panels in both flat and curved shapes containing multiple through-the-width delaminations. An analytical model was developed during the investigation. The model consists of a structural analysis and a fracture analysis. A finite element code, designated as PDTUBE-II, was developed for simulating buckling and post-buckling behavior of flat and curved delaminated composite panels.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a flat panel or a long cylindrical shell panel made of fiber-reinforced laminated composites subjected to compressive loadings, as shown in Fig. 1. The panel may contain either one or two strips of delaminations throughout the panel (see Fig. 1). For the given configuration and the loading condition, it was desired to obtain the following information:

- (1). the buckling and post-buckling behavior of the panel;
- (2). the interaction between the delamination growth and collapse of the panel.

METHOD OF APPROACH

The proposed analysis consists of a large deformation analysis for analyzing global deformations of the structure beyond buckling, and a fracture analysis for evaluating delamination growth caused by the deformations. A Lagrange multiplier technique was developed for analyzing the interaction between the upper and lower delamination surfaces during loading. Accordingly, the deformations and the delamination growth can be evaluated simultaneously, and the mechanical behavior of the structure, beyond buckling, can be simulated.

In this analysis, it was assumed that the length of the panel was considerably larger than its thickness, and the applied loads were also uniformly distributed along the longitudinal axis of the panel. Accordingly, a two-dimensional plane strain condition could be adopted. Thus, the free edge effect was neglected.

In order to evaluate both buckling and post-buckling behavior of the delaminated panel, a finite deformation theory based on the Lagrangian formulation was applied¹⁻³. Thus, the total potential energy based on the current configuration v^n in conjunction with the Lagrange multiplier technique can be expressed as

$$L = \int_{v^n} W(S_{ij}^n, E_{ij}^n) dv - \int_{A^n} \bar{T}_i u_i da + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \int_{S_\alpha} \lambda_\alpha f(S_\alpha) ds \quad (1)$$

where W is the strain energy function, and S_{ij} and E_{ij} are the Kirchhoff Stresses and the Green strains, respectively. \bar{T}_i are the prescribed surface tractions applied on the current deformed surface A^n , and u_i are the displacements. λ_α are the Lagrange multipliers and equivalent to the normal surface tractions on the delamination interfaces over the contact regions. A local coordinate system (s, t) was fixed along the lower surface of each crack (delamination), as shown in Fig. 2. The directions of s and t is tangent and normal to the lower surface of a crack, respectively. N corresponds to the total number of delaminations in the composites. In this investigation, only two delaminations were considered; hence, N is equal to two.

Note that, based on the proposed crack interface condition, slip could occur between the delamination interfaces, but the interface friction was not considered. In order to solve Eq. 1, a nonlinear finite element code based on the updated Lagrange formulation was developed. The solutions for Eq. 1 strongly depend on both the ply orientation and the generalized boundary conditions (force and displacements). Details of the derivation of the analysis and the numerical procedures can be found in Ref. 3.

In this analysis, the crack extension technique¹⁻³ was adopted to calculate the strain energy release rates for each delamination front for determining delamination growth. Thus, the strain energy release rate can be expressed at each crack tip as

$$G = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \int_0^{\Delta a} [u_i^+(a + \Delta a) - u_i^-(a + \Delta a)] \sigma_{2i}(a) ds \right\} \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND COMPARISONS

Numerical solutions were generated from the code to study the effects of delaminations on the response of flat and cylindrical composite panels subjected to compression. T300/976 graphite/epoxy was selected for the analysis. The material properties are listed in Table 1. Due to limited space, only some typical examples of the results from the study will be presented here. More results and comparisons between the data and the calculations can be found in the References¹⁻³.

Table 1. Material properties for T300/976 Graphite/Epoxy prepreg tape:

Ply Longitudinal Modulus	$E_{xx} = 22700000$ psi
Ply Transverse Modulus	$E_{yy} = 1320000$ psi
Out-of-Plane Modulus	$E_{zz} = 1320000$ psi
In-Plane Shear Modulus	$G_{xy} = 1010000$ psi
Out-of-Plane Shear Modulus	$G_{xz} = 1010000$ psi
Out-of-Plane Shear Modulus	$G_{yz} = 537459$ psi
Poisson's Ratio	$\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz} = 0.228$
Ply Longitudinal Tensile Strength	$X_t = 220000$ psi
Ply Longitudinal Compressive Strength	$X_c = 231000$ psi
Ply Transverse Tensile Strength	$Y_t = 7110$ psi
Ply Transverse Compressive Strength	$Y_c = 36700$ psi
Ply Shear Strength	$S = 16300$ psi

Figs. 3 and 4 show the calculated center deformations of cylindrical composite panels with and without a pre-implanted delamination and subjected to external line loading as compared with experimental results. The panels were made of T300/976 graphite/epoxy prepregs with two different ply orientations: $[0_4/90_4]_s$ and $[(0_2/90_2)_2]_s$. The delamination along the circumference of the cylindrical panels was 2.86 inches long and was located at the first interface between 0 and 90 degree plies, counted from the inner surface of the panels.

The calculations based on the model agreed with the data very well. As demonstrated in the figures, the load-deflection curves were affected significantly by delamination. The degree of such influence depends on the ply orientation of the panels and the location and the length of delaminations. It clearly indicates that delamination could significantly affect the response of composite curved panels subjected to external loadings.

Consider a flat $[0_6/90_6]_s$ panel containing two delaminations located on each interface between 0 degree plies and 90 degree plies. One delamination length was 3 inches and the other was about 20% shorter. The panel with two firmly fixed, parallel edges was subjected to a uniform compressive loading as shown in Fig. 1. The calculated load-shortening curve of the panel is given in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 shows the computer simulations of the buckling and post-buckling behavior of the panel during the entire loading. Clearly, the sub-delaminated layer with the larger delamination buckled first, but the panel could still sustain an additional load. As the load continued to increase, the second sub-delaminated layer buckled. By further increasing the load, the longer delamination started to propagate, leading to the collapse of the panel.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the results of calculations, the following remarks can be made:

- (1). delamination can significantly affect the response of composite shells subjected to external loadings,
- (2). delamination can substantially reduce the buckling load of pressured composite structures;
- (3). delamination propagation is initiated by buckling of sub-delaminated layers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The support of the National Science Foundation through contract MSM-8709270 and the Charles Lee Powell Foundation Award is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. Chang, F. K. and Z. Kutlu, "Delamination Effects on Composite Shells," Recent Advances in the Macro- and Micro-Mechanics of Composite Structures, ASME AD, 13, (ed. by D. Hui and J. R. Vinson), (1988), 71-77.
2. Chang, F. K. and Z. Kutlu, "Collapse Analysis of Composite Panels with Multiple Delaminations," AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS Proceedings of the 30th Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Mobile, AL, 1989.
2. Chang, F. K. and Z. Kutlu, "Response of Delaminated Cylindrical Composite Shells," J. of Composite Materials, (submitted).

Figure 1. Description of the problem.

Figure 2. Description of the selected local coordinates, (s,t) , for a delamination in composite.

Figure 3. The responses of laminated composite shells with and without implanted delamination. Comparisons between the data and the numerical simulations.

Figure 4. The responses of laminated composite shells with and without implanted delamination. Comparisons between the data and the numerical simulations.

Figure 5. The calculated load-shortening curve for a $[0_6/90_6]_s$ flat panel containing two delaminations.

Figure 6. The simulations of buckling and post-buckling response of a $[0_6/90_6]_s$ flat panel containing two delaminations.